

POWER POLICY AND CULTURAL DIPLOMACY IN THE TURKIC WORLD

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Annotation: *The article examines the theoretical and practical foundations of cultural diplomacy and soft power policy in the Turkic World. The concept of soft power is explained as states gaining international influence through culture, education, science, art and media without using force. The cooperation mechanisms formed on the basis of the common historical and cultural values of the Turkic states, the activities of organizations such as TURKSOY and the Organization of Turkic States are analyzed. The article specifically highlights the effects of soft power policy and the unifying power of culture in strengthening interstate relations. The results of the study show that cultural diplomacy serves not only to protect common values, but also to strengthen political and economic integration. By highlighting unifying elements such as common history and language, Turkic states expand cooperation both domestically and internationally through cultural festivals, scientific conferences and educational programs. In this regard, thanks to soft power policy, the Turkic World gains a more effective position in international relations and gains a strategic advantage by presenting its cultural heritage to the world.*

Keywords: *Turkic World, cultural diplomacy, soft power policy, TURKSOY, common cultural values, regional integration, common cultural heritage, strategic cooperation.*

Introduction. In modern international relations, the concept of power is not measured only by military and economic resources. Culture, education, art and sharing common values also play an important role in gaining influence in the world. This approach is called “soft power” and is based on creating influence through attractive cultural and spiritual values without using force. In my opinion, the policy of soft power serves to form mutual respect between peoples, and this produces more sustainable results than hard power. The Turkic World is a union of peoples covering a wide geography, connected by a common language, culture and historical roots. This union extends from Central Asia to Anatolia, from the Caucasus to the Balkans and unites millions of people. This policy is of particular importance for the Turkic World, because a common history, language and cultural play a natural unifying role between peoples [1, p.145].

Soft power and cultural diplomacy in interstate relations. In international relations, power is the influence exerted by one state on another to do something that it would not normally want to do. Today, it is observed that the most effective power is the ability to influence public opinion, persuade and negotiate, or soft power. Unlike hard power, soft power essentially encompasses politics carried out through partnership, cultural diplomacy and history; it is the ability to get what it wants by involving others without using hard power. This term was first used by the American political scientist Professor Joseph Nye to explain the possibility of states influencing the behavior of political actors through involvement and partnership. He explains soft power as a sustainable mechanism that increases the international prestige of states [7, p.45]. The main feature of soft power is its lack of coercive nature, and the means of influence are the dissemination of cultural values, ideals, visions, political values, scientific and economic partnerships. Wilson emphasizes that cultural diplomacy strengthens mutual understanding between peoples [9, p.67]. Another researcher working on the theory of soft power, Korean professor Geun Lee, divides soft power into 5 categories according to its goals:

1. The power that ensures a peaceful environment and creates an attractive image in order to ensure external security;
2. The power that ensures the support of another country or countries in terms of security policy;

3. The power used to manipulate the thoughts and preferences of other countries;
4. The power that ensures the creation of organizations or joining them for the purpose of cooperation with other countries;
5. The power used to ensure the internal support of the leader or government of the country [6].

Lee believes that soft power, like hard power, can be coercive or cooperative in nature. The difference between them lies in the use of resources. In other words, soft power and hard power are always related; soft power resources can in some cases increase or decrease hard power, and hard power resources, in turn, can affect soft power, and therefore hard power and soft power have a positive or negative impact on each other [8, p.20-22].

My conclusion is that soft power policy has its impact not only in interstate relations, but also in the daily lives of societies. Cultural diplomacy is like a bridge across borders; it connects people and allows them to gather around common values. For example, joint festivals, scientific conferences, youth exchange programs, and language courses allow people to get to know each other better. As Azerbaijani scholars emphasize, this process serves to preserve national identity and strengthen shared cultural memory. In recent years, Azerbaijan's soft power strategy has become more systematic and has become a key tool in shaping its international image [2].

Soft power and cultural diplomacy in the internal integration processes of the Turkic world. For centuries, the Turkic peoples have been connected to each other on the basis of common culture, language and religious values. In the Middle Ages, common literary examples, music and art forms brought the Turkic peoples closer together. In the 20th century, this process took on a more political dimension. In the late 20th century, new opportunities for cooperation emerged between the Turkic states that regained their independence after the collapse of the USSR. During this period, a number of states also tried to strengthen relations through cultural diplomacy.

Starting from the 1990s, cultural cooperation between the Turkic states, led by Türkiye and Azerbaijan, entered a new stage. The Turkish Cooperation and Coordination Agency played an important role in this field. As a result of the activities of the Turkish Cooperation and Coordination Agency, established in 1992, hundreds of schools, libraries and cultural centers were built, and thousands of students began to study in Türkiye and other countries through scholarship programs. These projects helped young people to assimilate common values, get to know each other better and lay the foundation for political and economic cooperation in the future. The agency has increased trust among Turkic states through educational exchanges, cultural heritage preservation, and social projects.

Established in 1993, TURKSOY has become one of the most important organizations of cultural diplomacy in the Turkic world. TURKSOY's activities are related to the preservation of common cultural heritage, and the promotion of folklore, music and art at the international level. The annual "Cultural Capital of the Turkic World" project has created an opportunity to organize joint cultural events in different cities. Various cultural events, namely concerts, theater performances, exhibitions, folklore festivals, are held in the selected city for a year. These events have strengthened mutual trust between peoples and served to strengthen a common identity. TURKSOY also supports the publication of joint literary samples, the translation of works by classical Turkic writers into various languages. For example, the works of Nizami Ganjavi and Yunus Emre were translated into a number of European and Asian languages at the initiative of TURKSOY. In addition, TURKSOY also implements important projects in the field of music. The "TURKSOY Youth Orchestra" has given concerts in various countries, introducing the musical heritage of the Turkic peoples to the world. This project has created conditions for young musicians to grow up on the basis of a common culture and gain experience at the international level.

The establishment of the Organization of Turkic States in 2009 created conditions for a more systematic implementation of this policy. The organization strengthens integration between member states through joint projects, humanitarian programs and cultural events. This approach serves both to protect national identity and to increase the international prestige of the Turkic world [5, p.102].

Although the Turkic world is built on a single cultural identity, each state plays a unique role in this policy. Their joint activities form a common soft power, but each has a separate contribution: Azerbaijan in the field of intercultural dialogue and multiculturalism, Türkiye with joint festivals, series and films, Kazakhstan in scientific and educational exchanges, Uzbekistan in the protection and promotion of historical heritage, Kyrgyzstan with folklore and national games, Turkmenistan in the fields of folk arts and national heritage, they are especially distinguished and demonstrate soft power.

Azerbaijan plays a large role in the cultural policy of the Turkic world. With its rich musical, literary and artistic traditions, it makes a great contribution to the common cultural treasure of the Turkic world. Examples include mugham, ashug art and carpet weaving. The Baku Process, initiated by Azerbaijan, has turned the country into the center of intercultural dialogue. This process brings together politicians, scientists and cultural figures from different countries and introduces the soft power of the Turkic world to the world. Azerbaijan plays a bridge role in the cultural policy of the Turkic world. With its historical heritage, Baku Process, multiculturalism policy and diaspora activities, the country both strengthens the common identity internally and increases the attractiveness of the Turkic world in the world.

The work done in the field of education and science is one of the most effective tools of soft power policy. After independence, agreements signed between Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan and Türkiye have created an opportunity for the formation of young people on the basis of common values. For example, within the framework of the “Mevlana”, “Farabi” and “Orhun” exchange programs, which were implemented to strengthen cooperation in the field of education and culture between Turkic states and ensure mutual exchange of students and academic staff, thousands of students studied at universities of Turkic states, which in turn created conditions for the spread of common Turkic culture among younger generations [4, p.5-12]. The Turkic Council, i.e. the Organization of Turkic States, founded in 2009, formulated the rules of cultural diplomacy in a more clear and concrete way. Cooperation in the field of culture and education was mentioned here as a separate item. Its activities are not limited to the political sphere, but are also aimed at the development of cultural diplomacy. As a result, the Turkic Academy began its activities in Astana in 2014. Here, the preparation of joint textbooks, joint research of historical sources and the publication of scientific publications were carried out. In 2018, Hungary was accepted as an observer member in Budapest, which strengthened the cultural ties of the Turkic world with Europe. At the Istanbul Summit in 2021, the Turkic Council was renamed the “Organization of Turkic States”, and new decisions were made to strengthen cooperation in the fields of education and science. At the initiative of the Turkic Academy, joint textbooks were prepared, historical sources were studied together, and scientific publications were published. This made a significant contribution to strengthening the common historical memory of the Turkic peoples and preserving national identity [3, p.1-7]. In addition, the Union of Turkic Universities was established in the 2010s, and joint scientific conferences and projects were implemented within the framework of this union. These events served not only to share scientific knowledge, but also to study the common historical and cultural heritage on a scientific basis. Turkey’s “Yunus Emre Institute” contributed to the formation of a common identity by opening language and culture courses in various countries. Azerbaijan, on the other hand, expanded international exchange programs through “ADA University” and other higher education institutions. These activities not only increased the educational opportunities of young people, but also led to the formation of a long-term climate of trust between peoples. From 2010 to 2020, thousands of students benefited from these programs, contributing to the formation of a common intellectual environment in the Turkic world.

Media and information exchange is one of the most effective means of soft power. Joint television channels, news portals and social media projects between Turkic states serve to strengthen cultural diplomacy. Information exchange contributes to the dissemination of common values, the formation of public opinion and the strengthening of interstate trust. The “TRT Avaz” channel, established in 1995, has become a common information platform of the Turkic world. This channel,

by producing programs aimed at the Turkic world, contributed to the formation of a common information environment with Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan and Uzbekistan. People began to get to know each other's daily life, culture and problems more closely. In the 2000s, joint news portals were created. These portals served to disseminate information about culture, history and art. Thus, information exchange between Turkic peoples further strengthened. In 2010, it was decided to finance joint media projects within the framework of the Turkic Council. This further strengthened the joint activities of the states in the field of information. In 2015, the Baku Media Forum was held. Here, journalists from Turkic states came together and agreed to strengthen information exchange. This forum strengthened both professional cooperation and the promotion of common values. At the Bursa Summit in 2022, the creation of joint digital platforms between Turkic states was discussed. This further strengthened the promotion of common values through social media. Young people are now participating in joint projects on social networks, sharing information about common history and culture.

In general, soft power policy also occupies an important place in the policy of Turkic states. In my opinion, the most important aspect of soft power is its voluntary acceptance, because no value accepted by force can be long-lasting. Cultural diplomacy and soft power policy are not only a means of protecting historical and cultural heritage for Turkic states, but also a strategic resource for regional stability and global cooperation [6, p.45].

The regional impact of soft power policy is manifested in the strengthening of political and economic cooperation between Turkic states. Cultural diplomacy increases trust between peoples, and strengthens the environment of stability and mutual understanding between states. Its global impact is associated with the increase in the international prestige of the Turkic world, the promotion of a common culture on a global scale, and the opening of new diplomatic opportunities. The joint cultural projects of the Turkic states are supported at the UNESCO level, which increases the impact of soft power policy on a global scale. The soft power policy of the Turkic states has begun to have a serious impact not only among themselves, but also in the world. This impact was felt most strongly in the field of culture. The production of joint films in the Turkic world makes a great contribution to bringing peoples closer together and introducing common values to the world. For example, films based on the epics "Koroglu" and "Manas" both preserve heroic traditions and bring together the film industries of different countries. Such projects strengthen the sense of common identity in the younger generation and serve to pass on cultural heritage to future generations. Joint films shown at international festivals are a living example of the soft power policy of the Turkic world. For example, the film "Nabat", a joint production of Azerbaijan and Türkiye, won awards at European festivals and introduced Turkic culture to a global audience. At the same time, events such as the "Turkic World Film Festival" are an important platform for the presentation of joint projects. Thanks to these festivals, the Turkic world not only promotes its own culture, but also strengthens the dialogue between different peoples. Since the late 1990s, Turkish music and films have been widely distributed in the post-Soviet space. People began to feel closer to the Turkic world by watching these cultural products. In the 2000s, Turkish TV series gained great popularity in Central Asia and the Caucasus. These series were not just entertainment, but also gave messages about family values, national identity and daily life. Thus, soft power policy began to influence people's thoughts and daily lives. In 2012, at the Astana Summit, soft power policy was already accepted as a strategic tool. The role of culture, education and media in interstate relations was especially emphasized here. The "Turkic World 2040 Vision" document, adopted at the Istanbul Summit in 2021, aimed to further strengthen soft power in the future. This document shows that soft power policy is not only a means of promoting culture, but also a key tool for strengthening political and economic integration.

Foreign researchers also emphasize the growing role of soft power policy in the Turkic world. For example, Hunter notes that Turkey's cultural diplomacy projects in Central Asian countries serve not only political interests, but also the formation of a long-term climate of trust [5, p.102].

Conclusion. Thus, as a conclusion, it can be said that cultural diplomacy and soft power policy in the Turkic world are important policy directions that play not only the role of protecting national

identity, but also a strategic resource for regional stability and global cooperation in the modern era. This policy allows the Turkic states to have a more effective position in the international system and forms a solid foundation for integration in the future. Although the unity of the Turkic peoples has historically faced political and military difficulties at different times, culture and language remain the main pillars that unite them. Today, the Organization of Turkic States carries that historical heritage to the modern diplomatic level. The organization's activities show that cultural diplomacy is not only a legacy of the past, but also a strategic resource for the future. My conclusion is that the Turkic world's future strength depends on the intelligent and consistent application of soft power.

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